

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SCHEDULED TRIBAL FARMERS IN VIZIANAGARAM DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH, INDIA

Anantarao Rallapati^{1*} and Dr. D. Ashalatha^{2*}

^{1*}Research Scholar, Department of Economics, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India

^{2*}Professor, Department of Economics, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Statistics related to the Andhra Pradesh STs can be used to explain the state of the state's tribal economy. According to India's and Andhra Pradesh state's demographic statistics, the decadal growth of scheduled tribes (STs) in India was 23.7% between 2001 and 2011. In Andhra Pradesh, this growth was relatively low at 17.8%, while at the national level, the ST population's share of the total population in 2011 was 8.61%, while in Andhra Pradesh, it was comparatively lower at 7%. 5.68 percent of the nation's ST population lives in Andhra Pradesh. The decadal growth rates of ST and general population from 1961 to 2011 both in the Indian economy and in AP state shows that, in both the cases of the growth of general population and ST population (except in the case of 1991 over 1981), the five decadal rates are relatively recorded higher at the national level. The fact that all five of the ST population's decadal growth rates, both nationally and at the state level, are significantly greater than the general population's decadal growth rates is another significant factor. In the instance of ST population growth from 1991 to 1981, the AP state's decadal growth rate is comparatively greater than the national average. According to data on the ST population's increase as a percentage of the overall population from 1961 to 2011, the ST population in AP is steadily growing over the course of several decades. Compared to another census, a notable increase was observed during the decades of 1971 and 1981. Given the census conducted between 1961 and 1962, the decadal growth differential is extremely small. A significant increase was noticed in between the decades of 1971 to 1981 when compared to another census. The decadal growth difference is very low, considering the census in between 1961 to 1971 and 2001 to 2011.

Keyword: scheduled tribes, Marginal Farmer, Medium Farmers, Small Farmers, Agriculture, Land

Introduction

About 80% of India's 67.8 million Scheduled Tribe (ST) people live in central India, 12% in northeastern states, and the remaining 12% in southern India. India had no policy in place to deal with the country's indigenous and tribal populations since the President of India issued the first notification to recognize the STs in 1950. According to the 2011 census, the STs made up approximately 86 percent of the overall population and continue to be at the bottom of society in every way. All STs were classified as primitive races by the Indian government.

The Scheduled Tribe is referred to as Adimajati, which translates to "primitive races," in the Hindi version of the Indian Constitution.

The first President of India, Dr. Rajendra Prasad, proposed Adimajati as a compromised translation for the Scheduled Tribe, citing its usage in Bihar. During the arguments at the constituent assembly, Mr. Jaipal Singh and Mr. A V Takkar argued that the Scheduled Tribe should be referred to as "Adivasi" rather than "Vanajati." The scheduled PTGs (Primitive Tribal Groups) are those PTGs or tribe communities that have been designated as such by the constitution order under Article 342 for the purposes of the constitution, according to Article 366 of the Indian Constitution. According to Singh K. S. (1994), there are 461 ST groupings that are recognized as STs. They were earlier described as aboriginals, primitives, adivasis and some other names such as Vanajathis and Girijans. Various tribal groups of our country are at different stages of economy starting from food collection stage to settled agriculture.

The proportion of ST males and females has been on the rise over the past few decades, according to the sex-wise proportional growth of the ST population throughout various censuses. Over the course of several decades, the growth of ST males has been comparatively higher than that of ST females. Compared to the prior decades, the growth for both ST males and females was larger between 1971 and 1981. Over 90% of the STs in AP still reside in rural regions, according to the rural-urban classification of the ST population over the years. Nonetheless, there is a discernible pattern whereby the percentage of STs residing in rural regions is steadily decreasing from decade to decade. Also it can be observed that inspite of the intensive implementation of development programmes towards development of tribal communities, the decline in the rural population was recorded very marginally during 2001 to 2011 census.

According to data comparing the literacy rates of STs with the general population in AP during various census periods, ST literacy rates in AP are consistently quite low. Nonetheless, throughout the past two census periods, the STs' male and female literacy rates have somewhat improved. When compared to male literacy rates, the STs' female literacy rates are still extremely low. Given the low female literacy rates among STs in Andhra Pradesh, it is imperative that female literacy initiatives in the state's agency regions be further intensified. The information relating to the number of ITDA, MADA pockets and Tribal Groups in A.P shows that AP has 8 ITDA, 41 MADA Pockets, 17 Clusters and 12 PTG Groups.

There are 33 PTGs in the state of Andhra Pradesh, which make up 6.59 percent of the total population. 29,683 square kilometers make up Andhra Pradesh's scheduled area, which accounts for 10.7% of the state's overall land area and 11% of the nation's total scheduled area. A diverse range of PTGs live in the tribal settlements. The Gonds, Andhs, Thothis, Kolanes in the district of Adilabad, Koya, Konda Reddies, and Naikpads in Khammam, Warangal, and Godavari and Bagatha, Valmiki, Savara, Gadaba, Konda Dora, and Kondhs in the district of North Coastal Andhra Pradesh, as well as Chenchus in Mahabubnagar, Kurnool, and Prakesam districts, are among the important PTGs. A large chunk of tribal population in the state is mainly concentrated in the 13 District: Srikakulam, Vizianagaram, Visakhapatnam, East Godavari, West Godavari, Khammam, Warangal, Adilabad and Kurnool.

The Government of India designated the Kolams of Adilabad and Konda Reddies of East Godavari, West Godavari, and Khammam District as PTGs in 1980, and the Chenchus of Ranga Reddy, Kurnool, Mahabubnagar, Nalgonda, Prakasam, and Guntur District as PTGs in 1975–76. Integrated Tribal Development Agencies (ITDA) are in charge of carrying out the central sector plans for PTG development. Chenchu, Bodo Gadaba, Gutob Gadaba, Dongiria Kondh, Kutiya Kondh, Kolam, Konda Reddi, Konda Savara, Bondo Poraja, Kondh Poraja, Parangi Poraja, and Thoti are the twelve PTG Groups (PTGs) that now exist in Andhra Pradesh. The majority of these PTG communities are located on the slopes and summits of the Eastern Ghats' interior forests. They relatively live in isolation of interior forests and hills. Still these PTGs are largely depending on food gathering, hunting, non-timber forest produce collection and shifting (Podu) cultivation for their subsistence and survival. In general the tribal economy in Eastern Ghats is agro-forest based and largely considered as subsistence economy. The population of the PTGs is mostly concentrated in the nine scheduled District. All these District, fall in the Sub-Plan areas of Andhra Pradesh.

Problem of the study

Improvement in the agricultural practices and levels of socio-economic conditions of tribals are sought to be examined in terms of endogenous and exogenous factors. At low levels of growth or stagnation of traditionalism perpetuates itself and internal growth impulses are very weak or non-existence. Hence in tribal societies extraneous (non-economic) factors play a significant role. Social change was the consequence of non-economic factors, but over a period of time in causation with the other proximate causes the internal growth impulses may be internalized in the tribal economy. All these factors work as prime movers of change in the

matrix of analysis as part of the process of cumulative causation. The analysis reveals that the improvement in the agricultural practices in the tribal areas has the complexity of process. The improvement in agricultural practices may occur out of the simultaneous efforts of all the exogenous (non-economic) and endogenous (economic) factors.

The Andhra Pradesh Tribal Development Project (APTDP) was appraised by International Fund for Agriculture Development (IFAD) in December 1990. The loan became effective on 27 August 1991 and closed on 31 March 1999. The total project cost was US\$ 46.5 million, funded by the Governments of India/Andhra Pradesh (US\$ 19.5 million), IFAD (US\$ 20.0 million) and The Netherlands (US\$ 7.0million). The cooperating institution was the United Nations Office for Project Services. The Tribal Welfare Department of the Government of Andhra Pradesh was the executing agency, with overall responsibility for project implementation.

Need for the study

Against this background, the researcher felt the relevance of examining the agriculture practices of the selected areas in the light of the agriculture development programmes implementing by ITDA of Vizianagaram district (Parvatipuram) in spite of APTDP with the assistance of IFAD and its follow up post project programmes in the scheduled areas of Vizianagaram District. The present day tribal situation differs from tribe to tribe. Their way of life and thinking are considerably influenced as result of various forces of change. A section of tribals become conscious about their rights and are organizing movements. Since independence, tribals are spread throughout India with their racial differences, region-wise study assumes importance. Hence there is need for more and more micro level studies covering selected tribal areas of the country to throw light on the efficacy of tribal development programmes in bringing considerable change in the economic status of the specific interior areas.

Quite a number of studies on tribal agricultural patterns brought forth the acute problems faced by the tribals. However, in most of the empirical studies the impact of non economic factors on economic behavior is not clearly brought out. In the present study an attempt is made to know the influence of demographic (Family size), socio cultural factors like value orientation on the utilization of different agricultural development programmes like Check- dam scheme and Land development programmes of ITDA in interior tribal areas. The study proposes to examine the variations as well as interrelationship between socio cultural

behavior and utilization of institutional development activities in the interior tribal areas, small tribal communities' economy cannot be completely differentiated from social life. An attempt is made to study the agricultural patterns in the interior tribal areas of Vizianagaram district in the light of the different agriculture development programmes like check dam and land development programmes conducted under the IFAD project.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze the resource base and features of tribal Sub-Plan area of Vizianagaram District.
2. Socio-Economic conditions of the selected Tribal Farm Households.
3. Impact of Land development Programmes on the Agricultural Practices of the Tribal Farm Households.

Methodology

The discussion on the methodology, indicate sampling method used, how the data is ascertained, the statistical tools used for analysis and to sort out the limitations of the study. Multi stage stratified random sampling method is used in the present study. There are four stages in which sampling process is carried out. The first stage is selection of district, the second stage consists of selection of mandals, the third stage consists of selection of villages and the fourth stage is of selection of households. After identification of tribal concentration in the panchayats from the G.L. Puram mandal, interior hill tract panchayats five villages are selected and similarly from the Komarada mandal five villages from the plain areas are selected for the study. As a whole 10 villages are selected for the in-depth study. For final selection of villages, the extent of coverage or implementation of ITDA programmes under AP Tribal Development Project (APTDP) is given weightage. Village-wise and year-wise programme implementation lists are obtained from ITDA office from which the sample villages are selected, bearing in mind the above point.

From the selected villages from G.L. Puram mandal for each programme, a total number of 75 farm households are selected as a whole, and a total of 150 households are selected from those five villages (from each village 30 households are selected). Similarly from the villages selected from the Komarada mandal total of 75 farm households are selected for each programme and a total of 150 farm households are selected from 5 selected villages to cover two programmes. Total of 300 households are selected from the selected two mandals of Vizianagaram District. As a whole the total of 300 households consisting of 160 marginal

farms, 100 small farms and 40 medium farms are selected from the selected 10 villages of the selected two mandals of Vizianagaram District for undertaking in-depth study.

DEMOGRAPHIC FEATURES OF THE SAMPLE HOUSEHOLDS:

In this section, an attempt is made to conduct an indepth study to analyze the demographic aspects of the selected tribal farm households. A sample of 300 households from the two selected (150 G.L.Puram and 150 Komarada Mandal households) Tribal farm households are taken. The sample of the selected Tribal farm households is in proportion to the village population. With the help of stratified random sampling procedure, a total of 300 sample households is selected from 10 villages. The details of the sample relating to the selected tribal farm households are presented in the following Table 1.

Table:1 Mandal wise, Programme wise and Farm wise Distribution of the Sample Households

S. No.	Category	G.L. Puram Mandal			Komarada Mandal			Grand Total
		LDS	Check dam	Total	LDS	Check dam	Total	
1	Marginal farms	40 (25.00)	40 (25.00)	80 (50.00)	40 (25.00)	40 (25.00)	80 (50.00)	160 (100.00)
2	Small farms	25 (25.00)	25 (25.00)	50 (50.00)	25 (25.00)	25 (25.00)	50 (50.00)	100 (100.00)
3	Medium farms	10 (25.00)	10 (25.00)	20 (50.00)	10 (25.00)	10 (25.00)	20 (50.00)	40 (100.00)
4	Total	75 (25.00)	75 (25.00)	150 (50.00)	75 (25.00)	75 (25.00)	150 (50.00)	300 (100.00)

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

From the above Table, the tribal households are selected in proportion with the respective village population. Across size groups of farms in total sample of 300 households, there are 160 marginal farms (less than 2.50 acres), 100 small farms (2.15 to 5.00 acres) and 40 medium farms (5.01 acres and above). From these households' primary data pertaining to different dimensions of their socio-economic activities is collected. The age of the head of the household will indicate his capacity to work and also the influence over the production capacity of the households. i.e. If he is too young he will lack experience and if he is too old he cannot work hard. Similarly the age composition of the family members also helps to assess the available work force in the family and its impact on production of the household. The programme wise and farm wise distribution of the heads of the households of both the selected tribal farm households in different age groups is presented in tables 2 and 3.

Table:2 Distribution of G.L Puram Mandal Households by Age

S. No.	Programs	G.L Puram Mandal					Total
		Below 25	25-35	35-45	45-55	Above55	
1	Land Development	12 (16.11)	17 (22.15)	25 (33.56)	18 (24.16)	3 (4.03)	75 (100)
2	Check dam	14 (18.0)	15 (20.0)	23 (30.0)	21 (28.0)	3 (4.0)	75 (100)
All Programs		26 (17.06)	32 (21.07)	47 (31.44)	39 (26.09)	6 (4.01)	150 (100)

1	Marginal farms	15 (18.73)	17 (21.23)	28 (34.97)	17 (21.32)	3 (3.75)	80 (100)
2	Small farms	8 (15.70)	10 (20.18)	14 (28.25)	16 (31.39)	2 (4.48)	50 (100)
3	Medium farms	3 (15.25)	5 (25.42)	5 (23.73)	6 (30.51)	1 (5.08)	20 (100)
All Farms		26 (17.06)	32 (21.07)	47 (31.44)	39 (26.09)	6 (4.01)	150 (100)

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

The above Table 2 presents the distribution of G.L. Puram households according to their age. A maximum of 31.44 per cent of households are in the age group of 35-45 and 26.09 per cent of the households are between the age of 45-55. The major proportion of the households is recorded in the effective age group.

Table:3 Distribution of Komarada Mandal Households by Age

S.No.	Programs	Komarada Mandal					
	Farms	Below 25	25-35	35-45	45-55	Above55	Total
1	Land development	14 (18.67)	15 (20.00)	27 (36.00)	16 (21.33)	3 (4.00)	75 (100)
2	Checkdam	11 (14.67)	14 (18.67)	26 (34.67)	21 (28.00)	3 (4.00)	75 (100)
All Programs		25 (16.67)	29 (19.33)	53 (35.33)	37 (24.67)	6 (4.00)	150 (100)
1	Marginal farms	13 (16.26)	15 (18.68)	28 (35.03)	20 (25.02)	4 (5.00)	80 (100)
2	Small farms	9 (17.88)	10 (19.87)	17 (33.77)	13 (26.49)	1 (1.99)	50 (100)
3	Medium farms	3 (16.39)	4 (19.67)	8 (39.34)	4 (19.67)	1 (4.92)	20 (100)
All Farms		25 (16.67)	29 (19.33)	53 (35.33)	37 (24.67)	6 (4.00)	150 (100)

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

The above Table 3 presents the distribution of Komarada Mandal households according to their age. A maximum of 35.33per cent of the households are in the age group of 35-45, 24.67 per cent of the households are in between the age of 45-55 and 19.33 per cent are in the

age group of 25-35. Like the G.L.Puram households the major proportion of the Komarada Mandal households are also recorded in the effective age group. As a whole it can be seen from the above Tables that nearly 75 per cent of the total sample households are in the age group of 25 to 55 years. Majority of the heads of households are in the age group of 35 to 55 years. In this regard significant differences are not found across different tribes and farms. The age composition of the family members of the two selected mandal tribal farm households i.e. programme wise and farm wise are presented in tables 4 & 5.

Table:4 Distribution of the G.L Puram Mandal Households Total Family Members by Age

S. No	Programmes	G.L Puram Mandal							
		Farms	0-15	15-25	25-35	35-45	45-55	Above 60	Total
1	Land Development	135 (37.60)	41 (11.42)	44 (12.26)	87 (24.23)	38 (10.58)	14 (3.90)	359 (100)	4.79
2	Checkdam	132 (38.15)	47 (13.58)	45 (13.01)	78 (22.54)	33 (9.54)	11 (3.18)	346 (100)	4.61
All Programmes		267 (37.87)	88 (12.48)	89 (12.62)	165 (23.40)	71 (10.07)	25 (3.55)	705 (100)	4.70
1	Marginal farms	145 (38.08)	53 (13.92)	46 (12.08)	89 (23.38)	36 (9.46)	12 (3.08)	381 (100)	4.76
2	Small farms	94 (40.60)	22 (9.50)	26 (11.04)	58 (25.05)	24 (10.36)	8 (3.45)	232 (100)	4.63
3	Medium farms	28 (30.43)	13 (14.13)	17 (18.48)	18 (19.57)	11 (11.59)	5 (5.80)	92 (100)	4.60
All Farms		267 (37.87)	88 (12.48)	89 (12.62)	165 (23.40)	71 (10.07)	25 (3.55)	705 (100)	4.70

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

From the above Table 4 it can be noticed that the family size of the G.L. Puram households is recorded 4.70. The family size is relatively recorded high in case of the households covered under check dam programme. In the farms, marginal farms are recorded high.

Table:5 Distribution of Komarada Mandal Households Total Family Members by Age

S. No	Programs	Komarada Mandal							
	Farms	0-15	15-25	25-35	35-45	45-55	Above 60	Total	Family size
1	Land	125	38	39	78	30	8	317	4.22
	Development	(39.34)	(11.85)	(12.32)	(24.64)	(9.48)	(2.37)	(100)	
2	Checkdam	120	44	39	72	33	8	315	4.21
		(38.10)	(13.81)	(12.38)	(22.86)	(10.48)	(2.38)	(100)	
All Programs		245	81	78	150	63	15	632	4.29
		(38.72)	(12.83)	(12.35)	(23.75)	(9.98)	(2.38)	(100)	
1	Marginal farms	126	50	46	81	36	7	346	4.33
		(36.39)	(14.48)	(13.25)	(23.39)	(10.47)	(2.02)	(100)	
2	Small farms	98	17	19	53	17	5	209	4.18
		(46.89)	(8.13)	(9.09)	(25.36)	(8.13)	(2.39)	(100)	
3	Medium farms	21	14	13	16	10	3	77	3.83
		(26.96)	(18.26)	(16.52)	(20.87)	(13.04)	(4.35)	(100)	
All Farms		245	81	78	150	63	15	632	4.29
		(38.72)	(12.83)	(12.35)	(23.75)	(9.98)	(2.38)	(100)	

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

From the above Table 5 it can be noticed that the family size of the Komarada Mandal households is recorded 4.29. The family size is relatively recorded high in case of the households covered under check dam programme and among the farms it is with the marginal farms, it is very low in case of medium farms and households covered under land development. As a whole it can be noticed that nearly 50 per cent of the family members are below the age group of 25 years. The classification also shows that most family members are in the age group of 35-45 years. On the total we can say that around 70 per cent of heads of the households are in the effective age-group 25-55. The average household family size 4.70 in G.L. Puram Mandal is relatively higher than the 4.29 of Komarada Mandal. The family size is high in case of marginal farms and among marginal farms around 40 per cent of the family members are in the effective work force. Among the family members of households, children and dependents are nearly 40 per cent; workers in the age group of 15 to 55 constitute around 60 per cent in total.

Age composition of various groups would only indicate the potential of work force and this factor alone may not be adequate in defining anything precise about the nature of stratification. Hence the data relating to sex wise distribution of family members is having relevance. The family members are classified into male and female and again sub divided into adults and children. The sex wise distribution of family members both programme wise and farm wise of the sample households of both the selected tribal mandals are presented in Table 6&7.

Table:6 Sex-Wise Distribution of G.L Puram Mandal Households Family Members

Programme/ Farms	Male			Female			Grand Total
	Adult	Childern	Total	Adult	Childern	Total	
Land Development	114 (31.93)	68 (18.91)	182 (50.84)	119 (33.19)	57 (15.97)	176 (49.16)	357 (100)
Checkdam	129 (37.39)	53 (15.22)	182 (52.61)	113 (32.61)	51 (14.78)	164 (47.39)	345 (100)
All Programmes	243 (34.52)	121 (17.19)	364 (51.70)	232 (32.95)	108 (15.34)	340 (48.30)	704 (100)
Marginal farms	127 (32.90)	72 (18.65)	199 (51.55)	124 (32.12)	63 (16.32)	187 (48.45)	386 (100)
Small farms	86 (37.23)	34 (14.72)	120 (51.95)	77 (33.33)	34 (14.72)	111 (48.05)	231 (100)
Medium farms	30 (34.48)	15 (17.62)	45 (51.72)	31 (35.63)	11 (12.64)	42 (48.28)	87 (100)
All farms	243 (34.52)	121 (17.19)	364 (51.70)	232 (32.95)	108 (15.34)	340 (48.30)	704 (100)

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

From the Table 6 it can be noticed that among the family members of G.L.Puram mandal households males (51.70) are recorded higher than females (48.30) and children constitute nearly 16 per cent in case of both the gender.

Table:7 Sex-Wise Distribution of Komarada Mandal Households Family Members

Programme/ Farms	Male			Female			Grand Total
	Adult	Children	Total	Adult	Children	Total	
Land Development	104 (32.70)	57 (18.01)	161 (50.71)	110 (34.60)	47 (14.69)	156 (49.29)	317 (100)
Checkdam	120 (38.10)	47 (14.76)	167 (52.86)	104 (32.86)	45 (14.29)	149 (47.14)	315 (100)
All Programmes	224 (35.34)	104 (16.36)	328 (51.86)	214 (33.83)	92 (14.47)	305 (48.14)	633 (100)
Marginal farms	120 (33.93)	63 (17.81)	183 (51.74)	118 (33.36)	53 (14.99)	171 (48.26)	354 (100)
Small farms	81 (38.59)	30 (14.29)	111 (52.89)	70 (33.35)	29 (13.82)	99 (47.11)	210 (100)
Medium farms	23 (33.33)	11 (15.94)	34 (49.28)	26 (37.68)	10 (14.49)	35 (50.72)	69 (100)
All farms	224 (35.34)	104 (16.36)	328 (51.86)	214 (33.83)	92 (14.47)	305 (48.14)	633 (100)

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

From the Table 7 it can be noticed that among the family members of Komarada Mandal households males (51.86) are recorded higher than females (48.14) and children constitute higher in proportion in case of male rather than female. Family members above the age group of 14 years are classified as adults. The workmen between age group of 25 to 45 are treated as effective work force. It can be observed that in both the selected tribal mandal farm households and size groups, proportion of male adults is higher when compared to female adults in the family. Out of the total family members, children constitute around 32 per cent. Along with sex ratio, the size of the family will also influence the productivity of family. Tables 8&9 present the programme wise and farm wise distribution of the households of both the selected tribal mandal farm households by family size.

Table:8 Distribution of G.L Puram Mandal Households by Family Size

S.No	Programs	Family Size			Total	Adopting of family Planning by household
		Lessthan-5	5-7	7 and above		
1	Land Development	20 (26.17)	39 (52.35)	16 (21.48)	75 (100)	30
2	Checkdam	21 (28.19)	40 (53.69)	14 (18.12)	75 (100)	32
All Programs		41 (27.09)	79 (52.84)	30 (20.07)	150 (100)	62

1	Marginal farms	19 (23.75)	44 (55.00)	17 (21.25)	80 (100)	33
2	Small farms	15 (30.00)	25 (50.00)	10 (20.00)	50 (100)	22
3	Medium farms	7 (33.90)	10 (50.85)	3 (15.25)	20 (100)	7
All Farms		41 (27.09)	79 (52.84)	30 (20.07)	150 (100)	62

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

From the Table 8 it can be noticed that among the family members of G.L.Puram households, 27.09 per cent of households are having the family size less than 5, a major proportion of 52.84 per cent are having the family size 5-7 and 20.07 per cent of households are recorded with the high family size of 7 and above.

Table:9 Distribution of Komarada Mandal Households by Family Size

S.No	Programs	Family size			Total	Adopting of family Planning by household
		Lessthan-5	5-7	7 and above		
1	Land Development	26 (34.23)	36 (48.32)	13 (17.45)	75 (100)	33
2	Checkdam	24 (32.00)	39 (52.00)	12 (16.00)	75 (100)	36
All Programs		50 (33.33)	75 (50.00)	25 (16.67)	150 (100)	69
1	Marginal farms	25 (30.67)	39 (49.33)	16 (20.00)	80 (100)	38
2	Small farms	18 (36.00)	26 (52.00)	6 (12.00)	50 (100)	25
3	Medium farms	6 (33.33)	9 (50.00)	5 (16.67)	20 (100)	6
All Farms		50 (33.33)	75 (50.00)	25 (16.67)	150 (100)	69

Note: Figures in Parentheses denotes percentages.

From the Table 9 it can be noticed that among the family members of Komarada mandal households, the 33.33 per cent of households are having the family size less than 5, a major proportion of 50.00 per cent are having the family size 5-7 and 16.67 per cent of households are recorded with the high family size of 7 and above. As a whole, it can be noted that nearly 65 per cent of the families have more than 5 members. The size of the family is relatively smaller in case of medium farms. The families with 7 persons and more are relatively more in cases of marginal farms.

CONCLUSION

The analysis pertaining to the demographic profile of the selected sample households reveal the following inferences. Across size groups of farms in the total sample of 300 households there are 160 marginal farms (less than 2.50 acres), 100 small farms (2.15 to 5.00 acres) and 40 medium farms (5.01 and above). The composition of the selected households shows that, G.L. Puram households according to their age. A maximum of 31.44 per cent of households are in the age group of 35-45 and 26.09 per cent of the households are in between the age of 45-55. Komarada Mandal households according to their age. A maximum of 35.33 per cent of the households are in the age group of 35-45, 24.67 per cent of the households are in between the age of 45-55 and 19.33 per cent are in the age group of 25-35. Like the G.L. Puram households, the major proportion of the Komarada Mandal households is also recorded in the effective age group. Nearly 75 per cent of the total sample households are in the age group of 25 to 55 years. Majority of the heads of households are in the age group of 35 to 55 years.

Across programmes much differences are not found; however, the households covered under horticulture programme are ahead of other households on the front of socio-economic indicators in case of both the selected mandal tribal farm households. Across farms, medium farms are ahead of marginal and small farms in case of all socio-economic indicators in case of both the mandals households. Finally, the analysis reveals the prevailing state of socio-economic backwardness of the selected farm households living in the villages in the very interior areas of G.L. Puram mandal are relatively backward when compared to the same farm households living in the villages of road side plain areas in the selected villages of Komarada mandal. In almost all the aspects the G.L. Puram Mandal selected farm households are lagging behind on the front of socio-economic indicators when compared to Komarada mandal households.

Reference

1. Bashan, A.L. 1985; "Wonder that was India", Bombay, Madras, Orient Longman.
2. Bhowmic, P.K., 1991; "Tribes in the Changing Circumstances of India", Man in India, vol. 71, No.1
3. Census of India, 1961; "The Census of Scheduled Tribe and Andhra Pradesh", Monograph series.
4. Doshi, Saryu, 1993; "Tribal India", Bombay, Marg publications.
5. Imam Bulu, 1993, "Cultural spatial concepts inflict in tribal art and identity in Hazaribagh District", Man in India, Vo. 73, and No.2.
6. Janah, Sunil, 1993: "The Tribals of India", Calcutta, Oxford University press.
7. Kosambi, D.D, 1981: "The Culture and Civilization of ancient India in historical culture", Delhi, Bombay, Bangalore, Vikas Publications.
8. Krishnan, P.S, 1993: "Untouchability and Atrocities", Journal of Social Action, Vol. 43, No.4
9. Kasipndian, P.S, 1996: "India that is Sidd", 1996, allied publishers Limited.
10. Luther, Narendra, 1990: "A Note on Indian Culture" (memo graphed copy) presented at the seminar for evolving a national policy for culture held at Osmania University, Hyderabad 14-15 September, 1990.
11. Marriott McKim, 1961: "Villages India"; little communities in an indigenous civilization, Edited by McKim Marriott, Bombay, Asia publishing house (pp.175-227).